

NEW DIRECT PROCESSING TECHNOLOGY FOR THERMOSET COMPRESSION MOULDED COMPOSITE PARTS: DIRECT STRAND MOULDING COMPOUND

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SUMMARY

In order to improve quality issues as well as to decrease the price for Sheet Moulding Compound a one-step direct processing technology has been developed. This paper should give an overview of this new direct processing technology as well as its characteristics and resulting mechanical properties.

Keywords: Sheet Moulding Compound, SMC, composite, compression moulding, direct technology

INTRODUCTION

Today, exterior panels for the automotive sector which meet the requirements for class A surfaces are often manufactured from sheet molding compound (SMC) material. The manufacturing process sequence starts by mixing resin, filler and additives into a paste in a discontinuous batch mixer. In the next process step, reinforcement fibers are introduced into the resin-filler paste, resulting in a semi-finished SMC sheet material. This sheet is stored for a certain time to allow the material to undergo a dynamic viscosity change called maturation before being formed into a component using compression molding with heated molds.

This process which is based on semi-finished materials results in deviations in semi-finished part quality and hence component quality. Therefore quality can only be determined after a certain period of time. Another disadvantage concerns the limited flexibility of the process. Formulation adaptations or changes will need several days.

The direct process allows certain restrictions on the processing of SMC to get rid of. Because D-SMC is a continuous process in which the raw materials are processed to a component within only a few minutes, it is possible to establish a control loop in order to guarantee a high and constant level of quality. The resulting reduced scrap has a positive effect on component costs. Component costs can also be reduced by the elimination of the maturation step. Another advantage of the process is that it offers high flexibility in terms of raw material selection and close-to-real-time formulation changes. Styrene emissions can be reduced for using encapsulated manufacturing equipment [1].

PROCESS TECHNOLOGY

The main idea of direct technology for thermoset compression moulded composite parts is to establish a continuous integrated process chain from raw material to the ready moulded parts. From the long fibre reinforced thermoplastics (LFT) the shift from a semi finished product technology to a direct processing technology is well known. Parts made of LFT used to be compression moulded based on long or continuous fibre reinforced semi finished products. In order to get rid off the semi finished product step a direct in-line compounding technology was successfully established [2]. As SMC can be considered as the thermoset type of LFT, the idea was to follow a similar process. For direct processing of thermoset compression moulded composite parts a two step process has been developed as it is schematically shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Process scheme of the new and innovative direct processing technology for thermoset compression moulded composite parts

Table 1 Typical SMC formulation for Class A parts

UP resin	58 phr
Low Profile Additive	42 phr
Dispersing Additive	1,5 phr
Air Release Agent	0,7 phr
Demoulding Agent	4,5 phr
Peroxide	1,0 phr
Inhibitor A	0,4 phr
Inhibitor B	0,1 phr
CaCO ₃	200 phr
Thickening Agent (MgO)	2,5 phr
Glass fiber	28 % wt

As SMC consists of up to a dozen raw materials (cf Table 1) a major point in the process is dosing and compounding them accurately. The shown processing scheme represents the pilot plant state, where the mixing of the liquid raw materials is done manually. This mixture of liquid raw materials is then being dosed, gravimetrically controlled, in the compounding extruder. This mixture consists of unsaturated polyester resin, low profile additives, processing and mould release additives, peroxides and inhibitor. The filler, which mostly is CaCO_3 , is then gravimetrically dosed in a side feeder and fed into the twin screw extruder. A Dieffenbacher ZSE40 has been used, In the following a homogeneous resin filler additive compound is made. The achieved compound quality is higher than in a conventional dissolver process. In Figure 2 the mixing quality of dissolver unit is compared with the mixing quality of the twin screw extruder process. In the direct process, the resin filler mixture is prepared using a continuously mixing extruder. The liquid and solid raw materials are forced through this machine, thereby generating an improved mixing effect. The dispersing effect of the extrusion step can be increased by selecting various screw elements such as kneaders and spiked mixers. The amount of air inclusions are minimized because this is a closed mixing system. In addition, it is possible to establish a vacuum zone. It is possible to see that the fillers are finely dispersed and very homogeneously distributed in the twin screw extrusion step. Furthermore, the number of air inclusions is very small.

Figure 2 SEM images of a resin filler mixture processed using a blade dissolver (left) or a twin screw extruder (right); less air entrapments in the twin screw extruder process;

The resin additive filler mixture is subsequently being transferred into a second twin screw extruder, where the reinforcing fibres are added. A Dieffenbacher ZSG40 has been used. In Figure 3 it is shown how glass fibre roving are fed in directly. The roving is first passed through a system of rollers. The intention in doing this is to open up the fiber strands evenly so that they are fed in at the same speed across the entire width. The rovings are then fed directly into the extruder and are broken at a defined position using an edge in the cylinder of the extruder. This method of working in is very good for glass fibers because they break at the breaking edge. An advantage of this system is that the fibers are force-wetted. The forced transport of the fibers also means that very high glass concentrations can be achieved. However, not all fibers break under all conditions, so that it is not always possible to achieve a defined maximum fiber length in the material.

Figure 3 Direct working in of glass fibers in to a twin screw extruder

As shown in Figure 4 a compact extrudate is leaving the die. For adjusting the part thickness it is cut into certain length with a certain weight. This extrudate is being placed on a conveyor belt. A robot picks up the extrudate and places it in the mould where the part being made. After compression moulding the part is demoulded. For compression moulding a Dieffenbacher press DYL630 has been used with testing plaque mould (460 x 460mm). In this new process lies only a period of a couple of minutes between raw material and ready moulded part.

Figure 4 Steps of outputting the extruded material, cutting to length and compression molding during the manufacture of an SMC component in the direct process

PROPERTIES

In the following a general overview of the mechanical properties of the D-SMC material is given. As it is similar to SMC and Bulk Moulding Compound (BMC) material, the values are compared with each other. The fiber content is in all three materials 25% wt. The matrix resin is unsaturated polyester resin and the filler type is CaCO_3 .

In Figure 5 the flexural stiffness of SMC, D-SMC and BMC material is shown. SMC and D-SMC both bear a E-modulus of 9,5 GPa, whereas BMC shows a higher E-modulus of nearly 11 GPa. The reason for that might be that the BMC material usually

has higher filler content than SMC and D-SMC [3]. In BMC the typical filler loading is 250-300 phr, whereas in SMC the typical filler loading is 180-200 phr. So at the same glass content the filler loading in BMC is higher which leads to a higher E-modulus.

Figure 5 Flexural stiffness of SMC, Direct SMC and BMC all at a glass content of 25% wt

In Figure 6 the flexural strength of SMC, D-SMC and BMC material is shown. At a level of 150 MPa SMC can be found. D-SMC has a flexural strength of 135 MPa and BMC bears a flexural strength of 120 MPa. In conventional SMC fibre degradation by shear forces in processing only takes when compression moulding what leads to a high energy uptake. In BMC the compound is injection moulded. By using this processing method high shear forces at high injection pressures lead to fibre degradation. In the Direct SMC process intermediate fibre degradation in the extrusion fibre compounding step takes places. As it is known that the flexural strength is dependent on the fibre length [1] [4], this effect can be explained. The typical fibre length of SMC is 25,4 mm and the typical initial fibre length before injection moulding is 12 mm [3]. In Direct SMC a fibre length of 15-20 mm has been observed in the compound as shown in Figure 7. Therefore from the extruded D-SMC compound the glass fibres have been washed out and the remaining fibres have been measured under light microscope. Beside the fibre length a fibre length distribution can be observed. This is an artefact of the extrusion step, where the roving is breaking inside the extruder barrel.

Figure 6 Flexural strength of SMC, Direct SMC and BMC all at a glass content of 25% wt

Figure 7 Washed out and measured fibres from the extruded D-SMC compound

CONCLUSION

Direct SMC technology represents a process in which SMC is manufactured in a consistent and continuous direct process. The manufacturing time between the raw material and component has been reduced from several days to several minutes. Also it has been possible to show that the filler distribution within the resin additive mixture can be made more homogeneous. Equally, it has been shown that the extrusion step does not have a negative effect on flexural strength. Furthermore, a strand can be extruded that is capable of being handled and can be pressed directly.

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